

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PHARMACEUTICAL AND BIOTECHNOLOGICAL INDUSTRY

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Relevance: Artificial Intelligence in combination with pharmacy and biotechnology creates powerful tandem, which hastens the development of this industry and opens new opportunities in medicine and healthcare system, altogether. AI precipitously changes these two spheres, by impacting production process, optimization of clinical researches and personalization of medical treatment.

Aim of research: 1) To investigate the transformative impact of Artificial Intelligence on the pharmaceutical and biotechnological industries, focusing on its applications, benefits, challenges, and future perspectives.

2) Analyze the various applications of AI in drug discovery and development.

3) Explore the integration of AI in biomanufacturing and bioprocessing.

4) Evaluate the application of AI in clinical trials and healthcare.

5) Identify the challenges and ethical considerations associated with AI implementation.

6) Discuss the future perspectives and potential impact of AI on the industry.

Research Methodology:

Literature review: A comprehensive analysis of existing research papers, industry reports, and case studies.

Expert interviews: Interviews with leading researchers, industry professionals, and policymakers.

Data analysis: Analysis of real-world data on AI applications in the pharmaceutical and biotechnological industries.

Case studies: Examination of specific examples of successful AI implementation in the industry.

Results: AI models optimize biomanufacturing processes such as cell culture and protein purification, improving efficiency and quality, in addition to this AI helps to develop personalized biologics tailored to individual patient characteristics. Also it facilitates the creation of novel biomaterials with unique properties for drug delivery, tissue engineering and medical devices. AI tools help efficiently find suitable patients for clinical trials, reducing recruitment time and costs. AI analyzes data from clinical trials, identifying patterns, predicting outcomes, and personalizing treatment. Not to mention the fact that AI models help to predict disease risk, diagnose diseases early and predict disease course, enabling preventive measures and improving patient outcomes.

Conclusion: All in all, Artificial Intelligence is playing an increasingly important role in pharmaceuticals and biotechnology, opening up new opportunities to improve people's health and quality of life. The combination of AI and biotechnology is a powerful driver of progress in medicine and healthcare. This symbiosis opens up new opportunities for the development of

innovative medicines, diagnosis and treatment of diseases, and the development of personalized medicine, which ultimately leads to improved human health and well-being.

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